

Use of Zwitterionic-type molten salt at room temperature for the one-pot synthesis of N-substituted decahydroacridine-1,8-diones in aqueous-ethanol

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Abstract : Zwitterionic-type molten salt – 4-(1-imidazolium) butane sulfonate acts as an excellent catalyst for the synthesis of N-substituted decahydroacridine-1,8-diones through condensation of dimedone, aromatic aldehyde and amine via multi-component condensation strategy in aqueous-ethanol as solvent. The key advantages of this process are high yields, room-temperature reaction, reusability of catalyst, environmental friendliness, easy work-up and purification of products by non-chromatographic methods.

Keywords : Zwitterionic-type molten salt, acridines, multi-component reactions, one-pot.

Introduction

In recent years, the use of economically and environmentally friendly reagents have attracted tremendous interest to carry out various organic transformations. Zwitterionic-type molten salt – 4-(1-imidazolium) butane sulfonate acts as an excellent catalyst as it makes the process clean, safe, eco-friendly and inexpensive. We have successfully applied Zwitterionic-type molten salt – 4-(1-imidazolium) butane sulfonate as a catalyst to develop different novel synthetic methodologies¹. Substituted acridines and its derivatives have attracted strong interest for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases such as heart defibrillation² and hypertension³ and also used as calcium β -blocker⁴, antimalarials⁵ etc. These compound also exhibit industrial application especially for the production of organic dyes⁶. Several methods are available for the synthesis of tricyclic compounds containing the 1,4-dihydropyridines, such as acridine derivatives from aldehyde, dimedone and ammonium acetate or amine via traditional heating in organic solvents⁷ in presence of different catalyst such as Amberlyst-15⁸, triethylbenzylammonium chloride (TEBAC)⁹, under microwave irradiation¹⁰, silica-bonded N-propyl sulfamic acid (SBNPSA)¹¹, *p*-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA) in water¹², ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)¹³ and ionic liquid¹⁴.

Although these methodologies are quite useful, many of these methodologies suffer from one or more disadvantages such as the use of expensive reagents which are difficult to recover and recycle, longer reaction times, high temperature, tedious separation procedures and use of organic solvents which are a threat to the environment due to their pyrophoric nature, volatility, and poor recovery. Ionic liquids which have been used for the synthesis of such compounds require tedious preparation procedure and their environmental impact is still in debate.

Recently Li-Min Wang *et al.*¹⁵ used Brønsted acidic imidazolium salts containing perfluoroalkyl tails as a useful catalyst for the one-pot synthesis of 1,8-dioxodecahydroacridines in water. Although the methodology is quite good enough but the preparation procedure of the catalyst is difficult and the reaction occurs at reflux condition and the perfluoroalkyl compounds are quite expensive. As a part of our ongoing program to synthesize small but interesting and potentially active organic compounds using ionic liquid and other simple reagents¹⁶. Herein, we have reported a mild, efficient and room-temperature protocol for one-pot synthesis of N-substituted decahydroacridine-1,8-diones derivatives by the multi-component reaction of dimedone, amine and aldehyde under aqueous-ethanol (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The reaction of benzaldehyde, dimedone and aniline was selected as a model to examine the effects of the catalyst (0–15 mol%) in presence of different solvents at room-temperature. The best result was achieved by carrying out the reaction with 1 : 2 : 1 mole ratio of benzaldehyde, dimedone and aniline in presence of 10 mol% Zwitterionic-type molten salt at room-temperature for 20 min (Table 1). We have examined the effect of mixture of ethanol and water (1 : 1). The reaction in presence of only water or ethanol decreases the yield considerably (15–20%). Higher amount of the catalyst or higher temperature did not improve the results to a great extent.

In a general experimental procedure, a mixture of aldehyde (1 mmol), dimedone (2 mmol) and aniline (1 mmol) was taken in a round bottom flask with 3 ml of aqueous-ethanol (1 : 1) in presence of 10 mol% Zwitterionic-type molten salt. The reaction mixture was stirred at room-temperature for a certain period of time as required to complete (TLC). After completion, the solid residue was isolated through filtration and it was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the pure product as solid. In general, reactions are very clean and no isolable side products were found. A wide range of structurally diverse aromatic aldehydes and amines underwent condensation by this procedure to provide substituted acridine derivatives in good yields. The results are summarized in Table 2.

As evident from the results, this procedure is uniformly effective for both aniline and benzyl amine. The aliphatic aldehydes such as propanaldehyde, *iso*-butyraldehyde, and cyclohexanecarboxaldehyde were subjected under the reaction conditions but no desired products were isolated. Aromatic aldehydes with both activating and

Table 1. Optimization of catalyst loading and temperature

Entry	Catalyst (mol%)	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	–	Aqueous-ethanol (1 : 1)	RT	20	< 10
2	5	"	"	20	72
3	10	"	"	20	96
4	15	"	"	20	95
5	20	"	"	20	96
6	15	"	80	20	97
7	10	"	100	20	96
8	10	Water	RT	20	65
9	10	Ethanol	RT	20	70

Table 2. Preparation of N-substituted decahydroacridine-1,8-diones in aqueous-ethanol

Entry	Dicarbonyl	Aldehyde	Amine	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^a	Ref.
1				30	96	13
2				40	92	13
3				30	89	13
4				20	95	13
5				30	94	15
6				30	90	15
7				45	90	8

Table-2 (contd.)

8		20	94	8		
9		15	95	15		
10		40	89	-		
11		20	95	8		
12		40	89	8		
13		60	80	14		
14		20	96	13		
15		25	96	13		
16		20	95	13		
17		15	94	13		

^aIsolated yield.

deactivating groups such as OMe, Cl, OH and NO₂ reacted to afford the corresponding products. The scope of the reaction was examined to explore the reactivity of simple cyclohexane 1,3-dione (Entry 14–17) with different aldehyde and aniline under the similar reaction conditions. We are pleased to report that it is equally effective in terms of time and yield of this three component coupling.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have developed an improved and environmentally benign alternatives for the synthesis of N-substituted decahydroacridine-1,8-diones through the one-pot condensation of dimedone, aromatic aldehydes and amines. High yields, mild reaction conditions, easy work-up, non chromatographic purification procedure,

inexpensive reagents and environmentally friendly nature are the main advantages of the present procedure.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a glass disk with an electrical bath and were uncorrected. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were run in CDCl₃ solutions. IR spectra were taken as KBr pellets in a Shimadzu 8400S FTIR. All the products were characterized by comparing with authentic sample and the spectral data of the compound (Entry10) which has not been reported in literature are given below for ready references.

Typical procedure for the synthesis of 3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-1,8-dioxo-9-(piperonal)-10-(4-methyl-phenyl)-decahydroacridine (Table 1, entry 10) : In the typical experimental procedure, a mixture of piperonal (1 mmol, 150 mg), dimedone (2 mmol, 280 mg) and 4-methyl aniline (1 mmol, 107 mg) was taken in a round bottom flask with 3 ml of aqueous-ethanol (1 : 1) in presence of 10 mol% Zwitterionic-type molten salt. The reaction mixture was stirred at room-temperature for 40 min. After completion, the solid residue was isolated through filtration and it was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the pure product as solid (430 mg, 89%); m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr) : 1363, 1481, 1602 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.82 (6H, s), 0.94 (6H, s), 1.85 (2H, s), 2.03 (2H, s), 2.21 (4H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz), 2.48 (3H, s), 5.17 (1H, s), 5.87 (2H, s), 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.88 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 6.94 (1H, s), 7.08 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.33 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 21.21, 26.75, 29.12, 32.10 (2C), 40.74, 50.12, 50.69, 100.47, 107.78, 108.65, 114.49, 120.80, 136.16, 139.46, 140.58, 145.47, 147.15, 149.93, 162.17.

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